

THE EPACT COMPUTATION: AN ALEXANDRIAN ACHIEVEMENT FOR ALL CHRISTIAN WORLD

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ABSTRACT

One of the many significant original achievements of Abba Dēmētrios I (12th Patriarch of the See of Saint Mark in Alexandria: 189-231 AD) was the method he devised for calculating the Date of Easter so that it would always follow the Passover, just like the Rest Easter Sunday, according to the historical biblical events. This method is known as the *Epact*, and to this day it is followed by all Eastern Orthodox Churches in determining their Easter date very many years in advance. It involved making a correlation between the lunar (Semitic) year and the solar (Egyptian) year. This was necessary because the lunar year is shorter than the solar year by eleven days, and a fixed date in it can fall in any season as the years go by, and would deviate Easter from the Passover. When Abba Dēmētrios performed the Epact Computation, he convoked the Holy Synod, and explained it to its Members. They approved it and decided to abide by it. Many years later, in 325 AD, when the 1st Œcumenical Council of Nikaia met, this computation was submitted to it, and was again unanimously accepted. It continued to be followed by all Christian Churches until 1582 AD, when the calendar was changed by Pope Gregorius XIII of Rome. Since then the Western Churches departed from it, and now they observe Easter on the first Sunday after the Full Moon following the Vernal Equinox, regardless of the Passover. All the Eastern Churches, however, still adhere to this old computation (*Computus*), hence the divergence between the Eastern and Western Churches on the Date of Easter celebration persists.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the many significant original achievements of Abba Dēmētrios I (twelfth Patriarch of the See of Saint Mark, 189-231 AD) was the method he devised for calculating the Easter date so that it would always follow the old Passover, just like the Rest Easter Sunday, according to the historical biblical events. This method is known as the *Epact*, and to this day it is followed by all Eastern Orthodox Churches in determining their Easter date many years in advance. It involved making a conflation between the lunar year and the solar Egyptian year. This was necessary because the lunar year is shorter than the solar year by eleven days, and a fixed date in it can fall in any season as the years go by, and would thus deviate Easter [FIG. 1] from the Passover¹.

When Abba Dēmētrios made the Epact Computation, he convoked the Holy Synod, and explained it to its Members. They approved it and decided to abide by it. Many years later, in 325 AD, when the 1st Œcumenical Council of Nikaia met, this computation was submitted to it, and again was unanimously approved. It continued to be followed by all Christian Churches until 1582 AD, when the calendar was changed by Pope Gregorius XIII of Rome².

¹ See WASSIF, 2006: 83-93; `EL-MASRI, no date: 39. In the current article the term *Epact* is used under the meaning of the *Metonic* or *Julian Epact*. On the life and achievements of Patriarch Dēmētrios, see e.g.: DAVIS, 2004: 21-22.

² *Ibid.* [EDITOR'S NOTE: Given that the Holy Fathers of the 1st Œcumenical Council were Theologians and not Astronomers, they accepted for that moment that very *Computus* until a better—one might appear in the future].

FIGURE 1: Two Orthodox Coptic icons: that on the left depicts the Resurrection of the Lord; that on the right shows Christ in His Everlasting Glory as *Pantokratōr* and as the Beginning and the End of everything (Α-Ω). The Resurrection of Christ and the Easter is the most important Holy Feast for the Eastern Orthodox Churches, which celebrate it in a joyful way after a long fasting and prayer period. Thus, the computation of the Easter Epact becomes very important.

Easter is the greatest and earliest feast of the Church, at which Christians celebrate the anniversary of the Resurrection of Jesus Christ and His victory over death [FIG. 1-2]. The observance of Easter started as early as the Apostolic Era. Writing to the Corinthians, probably at or near the Passover season, Saint Paul declares³:

Christ, our paschal lamb, has been creviced. Let us, therefore, celebrate the festival, not with the old leaven, the leaven of malice and evil, but with the unleavened bread of sincerity and truth.

In the course of their celebration of Easter, the Fathers gave it various designations. Justin the Martyr (100-165 AD) called it *The Paschal Feast*. To Cyril of Jerusalem (315-386 AD) it was the *Holy Day of Salvation*, while Grēgorios of Nazianzos (323-389 AD) called it *The Queen of Days, the Feast of Feasts, and the Solemnity of Solemnities*. After the waves of persecution had subsided and Christianity became the official religion of the Empire, Easter was celebrated on a grand scale. Eusebios, Bishop of Kaisareia, described the participation of the Emperor and Saint Constantine the Great who changed the holy night vigil into a brightness like that of day, by causing waxen tapers to be lighted throughout the city; besides torches everywhere diffused their light, so as to impart to this Mystic Vigil a brilliant splendour beyond that day⁴. During the first three centuries there was divergence among the Churches about the date of celebrating Christ's Resurrection. In Asia Minor, Northern Syria and Mesopotamia, the Church used to

³ See 1 Cor., 5: 7-8.

⁴ See BASILIOS (ARCHBISHOP), 1991: 1104.

commemorate the Crucifixion on 14 Nisan and to celebrate the Resurrection on 16 Nisan, irrespective of the day of the week on which these two dates fell. The Churches of Egypt, Italy, Hellas, Palestine, and Africa were particular about commemorating the Crucifixion on Friday and celebrating the Resurrection on the Sunday following 14 and 16 Nisan, respectively⁵. Actually in Egypt, Patriarch Dēmētrios I (189-231 AD) devised the *Epact* method of calculating the exact Day of Easter Sunday, so that it would always follow the *Old Testament* Passover, in close adherence to the First Easter [FIG. 2].

II. THE HISTORICAL TRADITION

The historian Saʿīd Ibn ʿal-Baṭrīq, Melchite Patriarch of Alexandria (933-940 AD), tells us in his *History* that⁶:

At this period, Dēmētrios, the Patriarch of Alexandria, wrote to Aghapios, Bishop of Jerusalem, to Maximos, Patriarch of Antioch, and to Viktōr, Patriarch of Rome concerning the calculation of the Easter of Christians and their fast, so as to know how to calculate them from the Passover of the Old Testament. Numerous books and epistles were composed on this subject, until the Easter of Christians was fixed, as is done today. This letter was written in the year 202.

Strangely enough Mawhub Ibn Mansur Ibn Mufarrig makes no mention of this letter in his *History of the Patriarchs*⁷. However, the Coptic Arabic *Synaxarion*, composed at the beginning of the 13th Century AD, mentions it twice, on the 12th Babah and on the 10th Hatur. For the 12th Babah we read⁸:

This day also, there fell asleep in the Lord [...] our Father Dēmētrios, the 12th Patriarch of the City of Alexandria. This Saint was an illiterate peasant who did not know how to write [...]. He was filled with heavenly grace. He was acquainted with numerous Sciences, knew the Ecclesiastical Books by heart with their commentaries, and spoke on many subjects and Sciences. It is he who ordered the calculation of Epact and that of the Fast, and sent an Epistle to each of the Leaders of Rome, Antioch, Ephesus, and Jerusalem. When they were informed of this, they gave their approval and established it as a rule, keeping it effective until our days.

On the other hand, the entry for 10 Hatur reads as follows⁹:

When our Father Dēmētrios was made Patriarch, he was a peasant who knew neither writing nor books. God illuminated his intellect by Divine grace [...] and he composed the calculation of Epact, whereby the Fast and the Resurrection are worked out. He composed it in Coptic and in Hellenic language and then sent a copy to our Father Viktōr, Pope of Rome, one to our Father Maximos, Patriarch of Antioch, and one to our Father Aghapios in Jerusalem. When his letter reached the three Sees, our Father Viktōr, Pope of Rome, judged what was sent to him to be excellent, and it caused him great joy. He summoned fourteen learned Bishops from Dioceses of his jurisdiction and a number of wise Priests. He read the calculation to them; they approved it, accepted it, and made a large number of copies of it which they sent to the other Episcopal Sees. Holy Lent and the glorious Easter were instituted as they are today.

Therefore, we see that since the very beginning, from the initial conception of the Epact method, it was gladly accepted and approved by the various (at that time united) Churches of the whole Christian World. During that ancient era this rather simple and brilliant *Computus* was the best until then, thus its acceptance from the Holy Fathers who saw to the common celebration of Easter for all Christians was a matter of canonical solution, until a better method could be devised.

⁵ See *op. cit.*: 1104-05.

⁶ See SAMIR, 1991: 410; HARNACK, 1893: 330; BREYDY, 1983; BREYDY, 1985.

⁷ See e.g.: DEN HEIJER, 1989.

⁸ See SAMIR, 1991: 410.

⁹ *Ibid.* During the era of Patriarch Dēmētrios of Alexandria neither Constantinople as a city nor the Œcumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople were founded, but still there was a local Bishopric of Byzantium.

FIGURE 2: Two more icons depicting the Resurrection of Christ: that on the left side is a modern Coptic Orthodox icon that shows the descent of the Lord to *Hadēs* and the salvation of Adam and Eve; that on the right side is a Byzantine Orthodox fresque from the Holy Monastery of Chōra in Constantinople and shows the same theme in a glorious way. In both icons the Netherworld/*Hadēs* is definitely vanquished and his doors and keys are overthrown by the victory of Jesus Christ against death and evil.

III. THE LITURGICAL TRADITION

The following *Tarh* (Peace Hymn) is sung in the Coptic Liturgy on the feast of Saint Dēmētrios¹⁰:

*Hail to Dēmētrios, who ordered abstinence from drink, and organized fasting from foods for the fifty days!
 Had this not been under the inspiration of the Spirit who reveals, how could it had been possible to discover and find the computation of the periods of time called Epact.
 Hail to you, o Priests, be thanked and praised for having come with diligence and without delay to the meeting place of the Council,
 Where the calculation of Epact dictated by the Holy Spirit was communicated to you by the venerable Dēmētrios.
 Hail, o Dēmētrios, to your hands that wrote the computation of past Epacts and that of future Epacts.*

The previous text, a typical example of the Coptic liturgical literature, proves that the Coptic Church has praised Patriarch Dēmētrios I significantly for his achievements.

IV. SOME THEORY ON CALENDARS

The way the ancient Egyptians conceived and organized their year, as well as the inherent discrepancies of the Sothic Period are well known and studied¹¹. The ancient Egyptian civil year had 12 months of 30 days each, after which 5 more epagomenal days were added, so in total it had $12 \times 30 + 5 = 365$ days. The New Year's Day (*wpt rnpt*) was theoretically coinciding with the heliacal rising of Sirius. However, due to the fact that the *tropical* or *sothic year* (*rnpt nfrt*) has a duration of approximately 365.25 days, while the *civil year* (*rnpt g3bt*) has a duration of 365 days, it is evident that as soon as the years and the centuries pass, there will be a shifting and a discrepancy between the two years, a fact that the ancient Egyptian priests–astronomers knew very well, but never officially corrected, at least never before the era of the Ptole-

¹⁰ *Ibid.* Cf. also BURMESTER, 1937: 1-2, 3-4, 78-109, 505-549.

¹¹ See e.g.: VON BOMHARD, 2000; SADEK, 2001: 13-22.

mies (with the *Decree of Canopus*, inaugurating the *Alexandrian Calendar*). This discrepancy was coming to an end after approximately 1461 years, which is actually the length of the Sothic Period, at which event the New Year's Day was again coinciding with the 1st day of the 1st Month of the ancient Egyptian Calendar, that is the 1st Month of the Season of Inundation (I *3ht*, day 1), in later times the 1st of Thoth.

In his era Pope Dēmētrios I (12th Patriarch of the See of Saint Mark, 189-231 AD) he was able –under the guidance of the Alexandrian Church and of the Holy Spirit– to calculate the exact Easter Sundays and called this *Epact Computation*. The word *Epact* comes from the Hellenic word *Ἐπακτή*, meaning the difference between the civil and the tropical year and/or the difference between the lunar and the solar year. In modern Hellenic the same word is also a purely astronomical term, meaning the *Age of the Moon* (*Σελήνης Θεμέλιον*) during the 1st of January or during the 22nd of March every year, which is crucial for the determination of the Easter day, as we shall see.

V. THE EPACT RULES & THE CALCULATION OF THE EASTER DATE

Here we shall discuss the calculation of the Epact. In order to compute this, we must follow two appropriate steps: **1.** We must know the first day of the Coptic year; and **2.** We must determine the *Old Testament* Passover [i.e.: the Jewish Pesach (פסח)].

V.1. FINDING THE FIRST DAY OF THE COPTIC YEAR: Extract the Sun Cycle = Year – 4; divide the result by 28; Epact extraction of the Sun: Cycle of the Sun + integer quarter (i.e.: without fractions); subtracting 7 from the former, the rest gives the Epact. Today the appointment of a weekly schedule through the day starts on Wednesday. Thus, we have the following Table:

WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN	MON	TUE
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

An example (for the Gregorian year 2011, that corresponds to the Coptic year 1727) can clarify the previous: For the year 1727: $1727 - 4 = 1723$; $1723 \div 28 = 61$ (remainder = 15) is the Cycle of the Sun; Cycle of the Sun + quarter without fractions $15 + 3 = 18$; hence, the Epact will be $18 - 7 - 7 = 4$. Thus, it corresponds on a Saturday. As the Solar Epact in 1727 Coptic is 4, then the beginning of the year was on Saturday, according also to the following table:

TUT	SATURDAY	BARMOUDA	SATURDAY
BABAH	MONDAY	BASHANS	MONDAY
HATUR	WEDNESDAY	BA`UNAH	WEDNESDAY
KIYAHK	FRIDAY	APIP	FRIDAY
TUBAH	SUNDAY	MISRA	SUNDAY
AMSHIR	TUESDAY	AYYAM`AL-NASI	TUESDAY
BARAMHAT	THURSDAY		

V.2. DETERMINATION OF THE OLD TESTAMENT PASSEVER: Extract the Moon Cycle: years of the martyrs (i.e.: current Coptic chronology) – 1; we divide the rest by 19. Extract the Lunar Epact: we multiply the Cycle of the Moon by 11; we divide the former by 30. Let us see an example for this. For the year 1727, we shall have: $1727 - 1 = 1726$; $1726 \div 19 = 90$, remainder = 16; $16 \times 11 = 176$; $176 \div 30 = 5$, remainder = **26**, which is actually the **Metonic Lunar Epact**.

FIGURE 3: Distribution of the Date of Easter in most Eastern Churches [including the Coptic Orthodox Church (BLUE)] for the time span 1900–2099 versus the Western Easter distribution (RED).
 [Transferred from the web-site: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Computus>]

V.3. DETERMINING THE COPTIC EASTER DATE: We must subtract the previous Metonic Lunar Epact from the constant 40 (a symbolic number with great significance in both the *Old Testament* and the *New Testament*), thus we shall have: $40 - 26 = 14$. The previous result is the actual date of the Passover and is located in either Barmuda or Baramhat only by the following rule: if it is between 1 and 23, the Easter will fall in Barmuda; if it is between 25 and 30, it will fall in Baramhat, and cannot be greater than 23. The result of the previous was 14 and following the *Old Testament*, it happens on the 14th of Barmuda (Friday 22nd April). Hence, the next Sunday will be the joyful Day of Resurrection. Thus, in the Coptic year 1727 (i.e.: Gregorian 2011 – 284) it will be located on the Sunday 16th of Barmuda (i.e.: on the 24th of April 2011)¹².

SATURDAY	1	8	15	22	29
SUNDAY	2	9	16/24 APRIL	23	30
MONDAY	3	10	17	24	
TUESDAY	4	11	18	25	
WEDNESDAY	5	12	19	26	
THURSDAY	6	13	20	27	
FRIDAY	7	14/22 APRIL	21	28	

A simple equation based on special *Computus*-Tables [FIG. 3] can be used to calculate the Paschal Full Moon Dates (PFMD) for the Julian Calendar, that is actually used by the Eastern Orthodox Churches, as follows¹³:

$$PFMD = 36 - E + 30 \text{ (if } E > 16) - 31$$

¹² See HANNA, 1998-2005 (still unpublished).

¹³ See e.g.: SOBHY, 1941: 169-99; for a full mathematical analysis cf. ΚΑΤΣΗΣ, 1959; cf. also ΣΑΡΓΟΛΟΓΟΣ, 2007.

(if the result > 31 the month is April), where

$$E = (Y \bmod 19 \times 11) \bmod 30$$

and where Y is the year. Thus, the **Easter Day** is simply the **first Sunday** after these dates.

FIGURE 4: The joyful Resurrection's greeting: *Christ has risen from the dead! Indeed, he has risen from the dead!* This is the beginning of the special Orthodox *Troparion* of the Resurrection of the Lord, the whole of which could be translated in Latin as: *Christus resurrexit de mortuis, morte mortem calcavit et entibus in sepulchris vitam donavit.*

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The controversy, nevertheless, continued. There was also a difference of opinions regarding the interpretations of the concept of the Crucifixion. To the Asian Churches, it was an occasion of rejoicing, on the ground that it heralded humans' release from the bondage of sin and death, while the other Churches, including the Alexandrian Church, observed Good Friday as a day of mourning and of strict fasting. This state of affairs was tolerated by the Church, as it was acknowledged that there was Apostolic Authority for both attitudes, the former deriving from Saint John and Saint Philip, and the latter from the Apostles Peter and Paul. The difference was settled in the 1st Œcumenical Council of Nikaia (325 AD), which decreed that Easter should be celebrated on the Sunday that followed 14th Nisan, after the Full Moon of the Vernal Equinox. The Church of Alexandria, the Great City that was famous for its expert Astronomers (e.g.: the famous contemporary of Kleopatra VII Philopatōr, namely Sōsigenēs), was entrusted with the task of computing the Date of Easter and it became the privilege of the Alexandrian Patriarch to proclaim the Date of Easter to all the Churches of Christendom, in a *Paschal Epistle* issued on the occasion of the Epiphany. Of course, it is to be noted that during that era the Church was united, thus we used the term *Alexandrian Church* (instead of *Coptic Church* meaning the Pre-Chalcedonian mia-physitic Church of Egypt, differentiated from today's Alexandrian Church, that is the Hellenic Orthodox Patriarchate of Alexandria and All Africa, definitely distinct from the modern Coptic Orthodox Church of Egypt), in order to denote this very fact. Finally, I would like once more to thank warmly Dr Amanda-Alice MARAVELIA (of the Hellenic Institute of Egyptology) and the referees (Rev. Archimandrite Fr. Geōrghios SARGHOLOGHOS, a known and esteemed specialist on the Calendars and the Epact Computation, writer of a concise related book and of several articles; as well as Prof. Dr Youhan-

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AMIN, M.: *La Langue Copte: II. Grammaire*, Nanterre 1996.
- AVENI, A.F.: *Empires of Time: Calendars, Clocks and Cultures*, NY (Basic Books) 1989.
- BASILIOS (* ARCHBISHOP): art. «Feasts Major–Easter», *The Coptic Encyclopedia* (Aziz S. Atiya, ed.) NY (MacMillan) 1991.
- BREYDY, M.: *Études sur Saʿīd Ibn Baṭṭīq et ses sources*, Lovanii (Peeters / *Corpus Scriptorum Christianorum Orientalium*, 450) 1983.
- BREYDY, M.: *Das Annalenwerk des Eutychios von Alexandrien: ausgewählte Geschichten und Legenden / kompiliert von Saʿīd ibn Baṭṭīq um 935 A.D.*, Lovanii (Peeters / *Corpus Scriptorum Christianorum Orientalium*, 471-72) 1985.
- BURMESTER, O.H.E.: «The Turuhāt of the Coptic Church», *Orientalia Christiana Periodica*, 3, 1937, 1-2, 3-4, 78-109, 505-549.
- CHAINE, M.: *La chronologie des temps chrétiens de l'Égypte et de l'Éthiopie*, Paris 1925.
- CRUM, W.E.: *A Coptic Dictionary*, Oxford 1939.
- DAVIS, S.: *The Early Coptic Papacy: The Egyptian Church and its Leadership in Late Antiquity – Popes of Egypt 1*, Cairo (The AUC Press) 2004.
- DE BOURGOING, J.: *The Calendar: Measuring Time*, London (Thames & Hudson) 2001.
- DEN HEIJER, J.: *Mawhub Ibn Mansur Ibn Mufarrig et l'historiographie copto–arabe*, Lovanii (Peeters / *Corpus Scriptorum Christianorum Orientalium*, 513) 1989.
- ʿEL-MASRI, I.H.: *The Story of Copts: The True Story of Christianity in Egypt*, Cairo, no date.
- FÖRSTER, H.: *Wörterbuch der griechischen Wörter in den koptischen dokumentarischen Texten*, Berlin–NY (De Gruyter) 2002.
- GRAF, G.: *Catalogue de manuscrits arabes chrétiens conservés au Caire*, Vatican City (*Studi e Testi*, 34) 1934.
- HANNA, A.N.: *The Epact Computation: Lectures to Seminary College Students*, Aswan Branch, 1998-2005.
- HARNACK, A.: *Geschichte der altchristlichen Literatur bis Eusebius*, I-II, Leipzig 1893-1904.
- ΚΑΤΣΗΣ, Δ.Ν.: *Τὰ Ἡμερολόγια καὶ ὁ Κανὼν τοῦ Πάσχα*, Ἀθήναι 1959 [with abstract in English].
- LEPSIUS, R.: *Das Bilingue Dekret von Kanopus*, Berlin (Wilhelm Hertz) 1866.
- MALATY, T.Y.: *Introduction to the Coptic Orthodox Church*, Cairo 1993.
- MALON, A. [S.J.]: *Grammaire Copte: Bibliographie, Chrestomathie et Vocabulaire* (Malinine, M., ed), I-II, Paris (Imprimerie Catholique) 41956.
- MARAVELIA, A.–A.: *Les astres dans les textes religieux en Égypte antique et dans les Hymnes Orphiques*, Oxford (Archaeopress/BAR International Series 1527) 2006.
- MARAVELIA, A.–A.: «Astronomical and Cosmographic Elements in the *Scalæ*: How Astronomy influenced Life during the Coptic Era?», *Copts and Society: Documentary–Historical Studies – Proceedings of the First International Coptic Studies Conference: Life in Egypt during the Coptic Period: Towns and Villages, Laymen and Clergy, Bishops and Dioceses (Alexandria 21-23 September 2010)* (Mansour, A. & Mahmoud, L., eds), Alexandria (BIBALEX, Calligraphy Centre / *Studies in Calligraphy & Writings Scientific Refereed Series*, 16) 2013, 187-202.
- MEYER, M. & SMITH, R. (eds): *Ancient Christian Magic: Coptic Texts of Ritual Power*, NJ (Princeton University Press) 21999.
- PARYSKI, M.: *A Study of Greek Loan–Words in the Sahidic Bohairic Dialects of the Coptic Language* (PhD Diss.), Michigan (University of Michigan) 1941.
- PLUMLEY, J.M.: *An Introductory Coptic Grammar (Sahidic Dialect)*, London (Home & Van Thal) 1948.
- SADEK, A.I.: «Le calendrier de l'Égypte ancienne», *Les calendriers et leurs implications culturelles* (Gobillot, G., ed.), Lyon (Éditions Lyonnaises d'Art et d'Histoire) 2001, 13-22.
- SADEK, A.I. & SADEK, B.: *L'incarnation de la lumière: Le nouveau iconographique copte, à travers l'œuvre d'Isaac Fanous*, Limoges (*Le Monde Copte*, 29-31) 2000.
- SAMIR, K.: art. «Book of Epact», *The Coptic Encyclopedia* (Aziz S. Atiya, ed.) NY (MacMillan) 1991.
- ΣΑΡΓΟΛΟΓΟΣ, Γ.: *Τὸ Γρηγοριανὸν Ἡμερολόγιον καὶ ἡ Στάσις τῆς Ὁρθοδοξίας: Ὑπολογισμὸς τῶν Ἡμερομηνιῶν τοῦ Πάσχα*, Ἀθήναι (Εκδόσεις Καλοῦ Τύπου) 2007.
- SATZINGER, H.: «Die altkoptischen Texte als Zeugnisse der Beziehung zwischen Ägyptern und Griechen», *Græco–Coptica* (Nagel, P., ed.), Halle (Martin Luther Universität / *Wiß. Beiträge*, 48) 1984, 137-146.
- SIDARUS, A.: «Coptic Lexicography on the Middle Ages: The Coptic Arabic *Scalæ*», *The Future of Coptic Studies* (Wilson, R.McL., ed.), Leiden (Brill) 1978, 125-42.

- SIDARUS, A.: «Contribution des *scalæ* médiévales à la lexicologie copte: Compte-rendu d'un projet de recherche», *Ägypten und Nubien in spätantiker und christlicher Zeit* (Emmel, S. et al., eds), Wiesbaden (Reichert) 1999, 390-404.
- SOBHY, G.: «The Coptic Calendrical Computation and the System of Epacts known as Hisab 'al-Abuqti, the Epact Computation ascribed to Abba Dēmētrios the XIIth Patriarch», *Bulletin de la Société d'Archéologie Copte*, 7, 1941, 169-99.
- TILL, W.: *Koptische Grammatik*, Leipzig (Otto Harrassowitz) 2¹⁹⁶¹.
- TILL, W.: *Koptische Dialektgrammatik*, München (C.H. Beck) 2¹⁹⁶¹.
- VON BOMHARD, A.-S.: *Le calendrier égyptien: Une œuvre d'éternité*, London (Periplus) 2000.
- VYCICHL, W.: *Dictionnaire étymologique de la langue copte*, Louvain 1983.
- WASSIF, R.: «The Epact: Exposition of a Manuscript», *Coptica*, 5, 2006, 83-93.
- WESTENDORF, W.: *Koptisches Handwörterbuch*, Heidelberg 1965-77.

